

**The new faunistical record from Bolu Province (Turkey):
Megalonotus praetextatus (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)
(Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Lygaeidae)**

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ABSTRACT: This paper is focus on *Megalonotus praetextatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835). The new record and distributional data are given from northern Anatolia (Gerede district of Bolu province) for this species.

KEYWORDS: Heteroptera, Bolu province, *Megalonotus praetextatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835), Turkey

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INTRODUCTION

Rhyparochrominae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Lygaeidae) is with 14 tribes, 372 genera and 1,850 species worldwide (Slater and O'Donnell, 1995; Henry, 2009).

In the palaeartic region number of Lygaeidae taxa is 225 genera 1001 species and 37 subspecies (Aukema & Rieger, 2001).

According to Schuh & Slater (1995) tribe Megalonotini (Rhyparochrominae: Lygaeidae) are most diverse in the old world, tropics

and palaeartic. And in this tribe eighteen genera and approximality 87 species are known.

Megalonotus praetextatus (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835) was by Stichel (1957-1962) keyed described and distributed information for this species was given. Also, approvals and distribution of Turkey data about this species have been given in the literature by many authors (Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Hoberlandt, 1955; Matocq et al., 20014).

In according to sources *Megalonotus praetextatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Lygaeidae) was first recorded in the province Bolu (Gerede district) in Turkey.

An imaginal male exemplare were found in June 2017 in Gerede/Bolu. After identification this finding has shown that: *Megalonotus praetextatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835).

This study were given the first recorded in the Bolu province of Turkey. (Fig.1)

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study was conducted in Gerede surrounding of Bolu province. A male specimen of this species was collected from a locations in the study area in 2017 (Fig.1).

The specimen was collected by sweep net on the herbaceous vegetation. It killed in 70% alcohol jars and were prepared based on technical and standards of data collection of the zoology museum.

These were determined using identification keys by Stichel (1957-1962) by second author.

Sample is deposited in the collection of the Zoological Museum of Gazi University (ZMGU), Ankara, Turkey.

RESULTS

Family : Lygaeidae

Subfamily: Rhyparochrominae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Tribe: Megalonotini Slater, 1957

Bull. Brook. Entomol. Soc., 52: 35.

Type genus: *Megalonotus* Fieber, 1860: Die Europ. Hemip. Halb (Rhynch. Heter.): 1-112.

Genus: *Megalonotus* Fieber, 1860

***Megalonotus praetextatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Habitat

The individual specimen of this species was found in the scrub and meadow areas at an altitude of 1338m in Bolu province (Figure 1, Figure 2).

According to works of literatures the specimens were found on *Cucurbita* sp., *Morus alba*, *Pyrus malus*, *Triticum* sp., (Lodos, et al., 1999) and *Astragalus* sp. (Kiyak, 2019).

Figure.1. The location of study area in the Gerede district (Bolu province, Turkey) of *Megalonotus praetextatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835) (★).

Figure 2. The sampling location is Yukarı Örenbaşı Demirci, Gerede-Bolu/Turkey (Photo by Ş.Şahin)

Figure 3. *Megalonotus praetextatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835) (Photo by Ş.Şahin)

Material Examined:

Yukarı Örenbaşı Demirci location, Gerede-Bolu/Turkey, 40°47'51"N 32°28'53"E, 1♀, 28.06.2017 (Leg. Şahin). (Fig.2, Fig.3)

Distribution in Turkey:

Turanico-Euro-Mediterranean (Péricart, 1999, 2001). Antalya (Finike), Gaziantep (Nizip), Kahramanmaraş (Andırın, Göksun), Kastamonu (Tosya), Kayseri (Pınarbaşı), Konya (Akşehir), Osmaniye (Düziçi) (Lodos, et al., 1999). Edirne, Kastamonu, Konya, Zonguldak, Kayseri (Erciyes dağı), Bursa, Gaziantep (Akbez), İzmir (Halkalı) (Hoberlandt, 1955). Ankara (Çubuk-Çubuk barajı) (Tuatay, Kalkandelen, Aysev, 1972). Adana, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bursa, Edirne, Gaziantep, Hatay, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri, Konya (Önder et al., 2006). Diyarbakır (Matocq, et al., 2014). Gerede-Bolu (in this study).

Distribution in Palaearctic:

Europa: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Turkey, European part, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldavia, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia (South European Territory), Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, Yugoslavia **North Africa:** Algeria, Canary Isles, Egypt, Morocco, Tunisia. **Asia:** Azerbaijan, Armenia, Turkey, Asian part, Cyprus, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Kirgizia, Lebanon, Syria, Tadzhikistan, Turkmenistan (Aukema & Rieger, 2001, 2013).

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In this study, *Megalonotus praetextatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835) was recorded and collected from Gerede (Bolu province), northern Anatolia, Turkey. This is the new record for this province.

In addition to the expansion of *Megalonotus praetextatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835) to a new settlement distribution, this study provides a better understanding of the species distribution in the Turkish

Heteroptera fauna.

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